

MF-PINNs: Mixed-Formulation Physics-Informed Neural Networks for the multigroup neutron diffusion equations

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ABSTRACT

This work extends a previous study of Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) for the one-group neutron diffusion equation in mixed form [1] to the more general multigroup setting. The multigroup approximation plays an important role in reactor physics, as it captures energy-dependent neutron interactions and intergroup scattering. As in the one-group setting, heterogeneous material properties can lead to low-regularity solutions, which limit the accuracy of the conventional PINNs approach based on the primal form. To address this issue, the Mixed Formulation PINNs (MF-PINNs) are developed for the multigroup neutron diffusion equation and it is demonstrated that this framework improves accuracy in heterogeneous media. Numerical experiments on several k-eigenvalue benchmark problems including the TWIGL and simplified C5G7 confirm the effectiveness and the accuracy of the proposed MF-PINNs.

Keywords: PINNs, multigroup neutron diffusion equation, mixed dual formulation, k-eigenvalue problem, core calculations

1. INTRODUCTION

The neutron flux distribution in the reactor core is determined by solving the transport equation which depends on several variables: three spatial coordinates, two angular directions, energy (or the velocity modulus), and time. It physically states the balance between neutron emission by fission and neutron losses due to the absorption, scattering, and leakage (at the boundaries) of neutrons. The multi-group theory where the energy domain is divided into subintervals called energy groups is one of the most common discretization of the energy variable. In practice, the multigroup diffusion equations are essential for accurately modeling neutron flux distributions and reactivity at the reactor core scale.

Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) have recently emerged as a promising and flexible framework for solving the solving partial differential equations (PDEs) where the physical laws such as PDE residual and boundary condition are incorporated directly into the loss function. In recent years, the application of PINNs to the neutron diffusion equation has gained great attention. For instance, a regularization method and a learnable parameter k_{eff} are investigated in [2] to solve neutron diffusion eigenvalue equations. Next, a data-enabled PINN (DEPINN) is developed in [3] to show that combining limited training data from physical experiments (or a finite element solver) with physical constraints really improve the convergence and accuracy of PINNs. In [4], fixed-point constraint PINNs (FC-PINNs) is introduced by using fixed-point transformation technique in order to simultaneously obtain the eigenfunctions and the accurate corresponding eigenvalues. Next, the physics-constrained generalized inverse power method neural network (PC-GIPIMNN) is developed in [5] for a k-eigenvalue problem with heterogeneous coefficients where the interface conditions are incorporated in the total loss function to ensure the continuity of the neutron flux at the interfaces. These works show the potential of PINNs for reactor physics applications. However, classical PINNs, typically in their primal form

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with only scalar flux as the unknown have some limitations when applied to heterogeneous media [1]. This is due to the fact that the PDE residual loss of the primal form is not well defined in the whole domain and one commonly has to deal with the interface terms at the interactions among materials. To overcome this challenge, Pinns based on the mixed form of the one group neutron diffusion equation is proposed in [1], in which both the scalar flux and neutron current are solved simultaneously with a neural network. The loss function of the mixed (dual) form is well defined over the whole domain which eliminates the need for additional interface terms. Furthermore, since the mixed formulation recasts the problem into a first-order system, its training cost is generally lower than that of the primal formulation with higher-order derivatives. On the other hand, enforcing hard boundary conditions is more straightforward for the mixed form than for the primal form. Therefore, the present work extends PINN methodology from the one-group to the multigroup neutron diffusion equation in mixed form and demonstrate its accuracy and robustness on benchmark problems.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: the multigroup neutron diffusion equation in mixed form is presented in Section 2. PINNs for the k-eigenvalue problem based on the inverse power iterations are discussed in Section 3. Section 4 provides numerical results for some benchmark problems to illustrate the effectiveness of this framework. Finally, some conclusions and perspectives for future research are provided in Section 5.

2. THE MULTIGROUP NEUTRON DIFFUSION EQUATION

Given an open set $\mathcal{O} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $d = 1, 2, 3$, we denote by $\mathbf{L}^2(\mathcal{O}) = (L^2(\mathcal{O}))^d$ the space of square-integrable vector-valued functions on \mathcal{O} . Let $G \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0, 1\}$ and given a function space W , the product space W^G is denoted by \underline{W} , for instance $\underline{L}^2(\mathcal{O})$ and $\underline{\mathbf{L}}^2(\mathcal{O})$. Let \mathbf{n} be the unit outward normal vector field to $\partial\mathcal{O}$ when the boundary $\partial\mathcal{O}$ is Lipschitz. Finally, it is assumed that the reader is familiar with vector-valued function spaces related to the diffusion equation, such as $H^1(\mathcal{O})$, $\mathbf{H}(\text{div}; \mathcal{O})$, etc.

For $G \geq 2$, let $\mathcal{I}_G := \{1, \dots, G\}$ be the set of energy groups. Let $\mathbf{q} := (q_x^g)_{x=1,d}^{g=1,G}$, $\mathbf{q}^g = (q_x^g)_{x=1,d} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ for $1 \leq g \leq G$, and $\text{div } \mathbf{q} = (\text{div}_x \mathbf{q}^g)_{g=1,G} \in \mathbb{R}^G$.

Let \mathbb{T}_e be the even removal matrix. At (almost) every point in Ω , it is a matrix of $\mathbb{R}^{G \times G}$:

$$\forall (g, g') \in \mathcal{I}_G \times \mathcal{I}_G, \quad (\mathbb{T}_e)_{g,g'} = \begin{cases} \Sigma_{r,0}^g := \Sigma_t^g - \Sigma_{s,0}^{g \rightarrow g} & \text{if } g = g', \\ -\Sigma_{s,0}^{g' \rightarrow g} & \text{if } g \neq g', \end{cases}$$

where $\Sigma_{s,0}^{g' \rightarrow g}$ are the Legendre moments of order 0 of the macroscopic scattering cross sections from energy group g' to energy group g and the coefficient Σ_t^g is the macroscopic total cross section of energy group g . It should be emphasized that, in general, the matrix \mathbb{T}_e is not symmetric.

The diffusion matrix is denoted by \mathbb{D} . At (almost) every point in Ω , it is a diagonal matrix of $\mathbb{R}^{G \times G}$:

$$\forall g \in \mathcal{I}_G, \quad \mathbb{D}_{g,g} = D^g.$$

where D^g is the scalar-valued diffusion coefficient of the energy group g .

The boundary condition is now split into three disjoint open parts such that $\partial\Omega = \bar{\Gamma}_D \cup \bar{\Gamma}_N \cup \bar{\Gamma}_R$. Then, the multigroup neutron diffusion equations in its primal form can be written as:

$$(PE) \quad \begin{cases} \mathcal{L}[\phi] := -\text{div}(\mathbb{D}\mathbf{grad} \phi) + \mathbb{T}_e \phi = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} M_f \phi & \text{in } \Omega \\ \mathcal{B}[\phi] = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $B[\phi]$ stands for the boundary condition (BC) of the primal form defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{B}[\phi] = \begin{cases} \phi & \text{on } \Gamma_D & \text{Dirichlet BC} \\ \mathbb{D}\mathbf{grad} \phi \cdot \mathbf{n} & \text{on } \Gamma_N & \text{Neumann BC} \\ \mathbb{D}\mathbf{grad} \phi \cdot \mathbf{n} + \frac{1}{2}\phi & \text{on } \Gamma_R & \text{Robin BC.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In Equation (1), $M_f \in (\mathbb{R})^{G \times G}$ denotes the fission matrix defined for all $(g, g') \in \mathcal{I}_G \times \mathcal{I}_G$ by $(M_f)_{g,g'} = \chi^g (\nu \Sigma_f)^{g'}$ where χ^g is the total spectrum of the energy group g , $\nu^{g'}$ is the average number of neutrons emitted by fission in the energy group g' and $\Sigma_f^{g'}$ is the macroscopic fission cross section of the energy group g' .

Under the assumptions for the coefficients [6], the eigenvalue k_{eff} (the multiplication factor.) with the greatest modulus is simple, real and strictly positive. Furthermore, the associated eigenfunction ϕ (neutron flux) is real and positive, up to a multiplicative constant.

On the other hand, the multigroup neutron diffusion equation in mixed formulation may be written as:

$$(ME) \quad \begin{cases} \mathbb{D}^{-1}\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{grad} \phi = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \text{div } \mathbf{p} + \mathbb{T}_e \phi = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} M_f \phi & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \mathcal{B}[\mathbf{p}, \phi] = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{B}[\mathbf{p}, \phi]$ stands for the boundary condition (BC) of the mixed dual form defined by:

$$\mathcal{B}[\mathbf{p}, \phi] = \begin{cases} \phi & \text{on } \Gamma_D & \text{Dirichlet BC} \\ \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{n} & \text{on } \Gamma_N & \text{Neumann BC} \\ -\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{n} + \frac{1}{2}\phi & \text{on } \Gamma_R & \text{Robin BC.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Solving the mixed problem (3) is equivalent to solving (1).

3. MIXED FORMULATION PHYSIC-INFORMED NEURON NETWORKS (MF-PINNS)

First of all, let us consider a source term $S_f \in \underline{L}^2(\Omega)$, the source problem in mixed dual form of problem (3) can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \mathbb{D}^{-1}\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{grad} \phi = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \text{div } \mathbf{p} + \mathbb{T}_e \phi = S_f & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \mathcal{B}[\mathbf{p}, \phi] = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases} \iff \begin{cases} \mathcal{L}[\zeta] = S & \text{in } \Omega \\ \mathcal{B}[\zeta] = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\zeta := (\mathbf{p}, \phi), \quad \mathcal{L}[\zeta] := \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{D}^{-1}\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{grad} \phi \\ \text{div } \mathbf{p} + \mathbb{T}_e \phi \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad S = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ S_f \end{pmatrix}.$$

In this work, the aim is to use a neural network as a parametric function with parameter θ that maps an input $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ to an output $\zeta_\theta(x) = (\mathbf{p}_\theta, \phi_\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ to approximate the neutron flux and current of the multigroup neutron diffusion equation. In particular, a fully connected neural network (FCNN) is considered, which typically comprises an input layer, L hidden layers, and an output layer as follows

$$\begin{aligned} h_\ell &= \sigma_\ell(W_\ell h_{\ell-1} + b_\ell), \quad \text{for } h_0 = x \quad \text{and} \quad \ell = 1, 2, \dots, L, \\ \zeta_\theta(x) &= W_{L+1} h_L + b_{L+1}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where σ_ℓ stands for an entry-wise activation function of hidden layer ℓ . The learnable parameters $W_\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\ell \times n_{\ell-1}}$ and $b_\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\ell}$ are respectively weight and bias associated to each layer ℓ with the number of neurons n_ℓ . Additionally, let $\theta = (W_1, b_1, \dots, W_L, b_L, W_{L+1}, b_{L+1}) \in \Theta$ denote the set of weights and biases that are optimized during the training process. In general, the objective function of the PINNs framework is defined by using the PDE and boundary residual in the L^2 norm. Therefore, the loss function associated to the mixed form (5) is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}[\zeta_\theta] &= \|\mathcal{L}[\zeta_\theta] - S\|_{\underline{L}^2(\Omega)}^2 + \gamma_b \|\mathcal{B}[\zeta_\theta]\|_{\underline{L}^2(\partial\Omega)}^2 \\ &= \|\operatorname{div} \mathbf{p}_\theta + \mathbb{T}_e \phi_\theta - S\|_{\underline{L}^2(\Omega)}^2 + \|\mathbb{D}^{-1} \mathbf{p}_\theta + \mathbf{grad} \phi_\theta\|_{\underline{L}^2(\Omega)}^2 + \gamma_b \|\mathcal{B}[\zeta_\theta]\|_{\underline{L}^2(\partial\Omega)}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\gamma_b > 0$ is a penalty coefficient. This method is commonly referred as the *soft boundary condition* since the boundary condition term is incorporated into the loss function. It is worth pointing out that the neural network with this *soft boundary condition* method does not exactly satisfy the boundary conditions. This may lead to the imbalance gradients problem of the training process. In order to guarantee the boundary condition, one can build a neural network in such a way that $\mathcal{B}[\zeta_\theta] = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$ which helps to avoid the imbalance gradient problem, as well as to improve the convergence of the optimization problem. In fact, one can introduce an extra modified layer as: $\tilde{\zeta}_\theta(x) := f_g(x, \zeta_\theta(x))$, where $f_g : \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^{d+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ is a C^1 function that depends on the boundary function g and Ω , which is constructed to modify the output function for the boundary condition. This method is commonly referred as hard boundary conditions (HBC). The methods proposed in [1] are followed to construct HBC for PINNs in mixed form, as the extension from one group to multigroup setting is straightforward. The k-eigenvalue problem is addressed using the inverse power iteration described in Algorithm 1. From an initial guess for the source, the associated source problem (9) is repeatedly solved until convergence is achieved. The value of k_{eff} and the source term are updated at each inverse power iteration (outer iteration). The MF-PINNs framework is applied to solve the source problem. In particular, one has to optimize the loss function of the MF-PINNs in high-dimensional space. Instead of working with the continuous loss function (7), it is common to approximate it by the following empirical loss:

$$\mathcal{J}_h(\zeta_\theta) = \frac{1}{N_r} \sum_{i=1}^{N_r} [\mathcal{L}[\zeta_\theta](x_i^r) - S(x_i^r)]^2 + \gamma_b \frac{1}{N_b} \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} [\mathcal{B}[\zeta_\theta](x_i^b)]^2, \quad (8)$$

where N_r and N_b , respectively, stands for the number of residual points and boundary points, $\{x_i^r\}_{i=1}^{N_r}$ are *residual points* which are randomly sampled in Ω and $\{x_i^b\}_{i=1}^{N_b}$ are *boundary points* randomly sampled in $\partial\Omega$. It is important to note that the sampling method (SM) for the collocation points in the empirical loss (8) plays an important role in the performance of PINNs.

Finally, the discrete loss function is minimized by solving

$$\theta_h^* := \arg \min_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{J}_h(\theta).$$

This optimization problem can be solved using the gradient descent method:

$$\text{For } j = 1, \dots, N_{\text{inner}} : \quad \theta_{j+1} = \theta_j - \eta_j \nabla \mathcal{J}(\theta_j),$$

where N_{inner} is the number of inner iterations, θ_j represents the parameters of the neural network at iteration j and η_j is the learning rate.

Algorithm 1: The inverse Power iteration

Input: The threshold numbers \mathcal{E}_ϕ and $\mathcal{E}_{k_{\text{eff}}}$
Output: The solution $\zeta_\theta^n = (\mathbf{p}_\theta^n, \phi_\theta^n)$ and k_{eff}^n at iteration number n .

 1 Set initial guess $(\zeta^0, k_{\text{eff}}^0)$, $S_f^0 = M_f \phi^0$, $n = 0$

 2 **do**

3 Solve the source problem :

$$\begin{cases} \mathbb{D}^{-1} \mathbf{p}_\theta^{n+1} + \mathbf{grad} \phi_\theta^{n+1} = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \text{div} \mathbf{p}_\theta^{n+1} + \mathbb{T}_e \phi_\theta^{n+1} = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}^n} S_f^n & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \mathcal{B}[\mathbf{p}_\theta^{n+1}, \phi_\theta^{n+1}] = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

 4 Update: $S_f^{n+1} = M_f \phi_\theta^{n+1}$, $k_{\text{eff}}^{n+1} = k_{\text{eff}}^n \frac{(S_f^{n+1}, S_f^{n+1})}{(S_f^{n+1}, S_f^n)}$

 5 Evaluate the residuals: $\epsilon_\phi^{n+1} = \frac{\|\phi_\theta^{n+1} - \phi_\theta^n\|_2}{\|\phi_\theta^n\|_2}$ and $\epsilon_{k_{\text{eff}}}^{n+1} = \frac{|k_{\text{eff}}^{n+1} - k_{\text{eff}}^n|}{k_{\text{eff}}^n}$

 6 $n \leftarrow n + 1$

 7 **while** $\epsilon_\phi^n \leq \mathcal{E}_\phi$ and $\epsilon_{k_{\text{eff}}}^n \leq \mathcal{E}_{k_{\text{eff}}}$;

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this numerical section, MF-PINNs are applied to several benchmark test cases. First, the TWIGL-2D benchmark, a symmetric seed-blanket problem, is considered with its geometry shown in Figure 1 and the corresponding cross sections presented in Table I. In addition, a simplified version of the C5G7 benchmark, previously studied in [2] with a total of 3 materials is examined. The geometry of this test case is presented in Figure 3 and the cross sections data are provided in Table II. The calculation of the reference solution is performed on a uniform 120×120 grid using the MINOS solver [7] of the deterministic code APOLLO3[®] [8]. The reference value of the multiplication factor is $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ref}} = 0.91320$ for the TWIGL benchmark and $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ref}} = 0.92757$ for the simplified C5G7 benchmark. A fully connected neural network (6) is used with $L = 5$ hidden layers and $N_\ell = 64$ neurons for each layer. Adam optimizer and multi-step learning rate is applied to the training process with learning rate decay $\gamma = 0.1$ for each 10^4 training iterations. The number of residual points is $N_r = 20480$ and the number of inner iterations is fixed at $N_{\text{inner}} = 2000$. Next, the stopping criteria are set to $\mathcal{E}_\phi = 10^{-5}$ and $\mathcal{E}_{k_{\text{eff}}} = 10^{-6}$. The hard boundary condition (HBC) is imposed to the neural network. For quantitative comparison purposes, let us define the following errors:

$$\Delta k_{\text{eff}} = 10^5 \times |k_{\text{eff}} - k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ref}}| \text{ (pcm)} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{\Delta} \phi = 10^2 \times \frac{\|\phi_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{\text{test}}) - \phi_{\text{ref}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{test}})\|_2}{\|\phi_{\text{ref}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{test}})\|_2} \quad (\%)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2$ is the Euclidean norm or the 2-norm, $\mathbf{x}_{\text{test}} = \{x_i^t\}_{i=1}^{N_t}$ is the set of test points.

According to Figures 2 and 4, the MF-PINNs provide a good approximate solution to both the TWIGL and simplified C5G7 benchmarks and there are small errors in the interactions between materials. Table III shows the influence of the sampling methods (SM) and the activation functions (σ) on the accuracy of the MF-PINNs for the multigroup equation. Consistent with the results in [1] for the one-group equation, Quasi-Monte Carlo integration with low-discrepancy sequences such as Halton or Sobol provides higher accuracy compared to Monte Carlo integration with uniform sampling (US) or Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS). Furthermore, the *Sin* activation function provides better performance compared to the *Tanh* and *Sigmoid* activation functions.

Figure 1. The TWIGL geometry

Cross sections	Ω_1	Ω_2	Ω_3
D_1	1.4	1.4	1.3
D_2	0.4	0.4	0.5
$\Sigma_{a,1}$	0.01	0.01	0.008
$\Sigma_{a,2}$	0.15	0.15	0.05
$\Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}$	0.01	0.01	0.01
$\nu \Sigma_{f,1}$	0.007	0.007	0.003
$\nu \Sigma_{f,2}$	0.20	0.20	0.06

Table I. Cross sections (cm^{-1}) for the TWIGL benchmark

(a) Fast group

(b) Thermal group

Figure 2. Neutron flux and the deviation from the reference solution for TWIGL benchmark with Sobol sampling method and Sin activation function.

Table III. Errors for benchmark test cases (TWIGL and simplified C5G7)

σ	SM	TWIGL				Simplified C5G7			
		N_{outer}	k_{eff}	Δk_{eff}	$\bar{\Delta}\phi$ (%)	N_{outer}	k_{eff}	Δk_{eff}	$\bar{\Delta}\phi$ (%)
Sigmoid	US	194	0.91300	20	0.136	263	0.92722	35	0.478
	LHS	182	0.91304	16	0.096	297	0.92737	20	0.222
	Halton	196	0.91304	16	0.095	189	0.92734	23	0.227
	Sobol	197	0.91301	19	0.132	235	0.92738	19	0.219
Tanh	US	133	0.91318	2	0.068	269	0.92746	11	0.213
	LHS	158	0.91312	8	0.079	230	0.92751	6	0.090
	Halton	226	0.91314	6	0.043	246	0.92748	9	0.126
	Sobol	234	0.91319	1	0.046	246	0.92755	2	0.063
Sin	US	230	0.91318	2	0.109	168	0.92751	6	0.070
	LHS	205	0.91315	5	0.049	219	0.92753	4	0.077
	Halton	233	0.91319	1	0.045	227	0.92756	1	0.052
	Sobol	211	0.91318	2	0.042	209	0.92754	3	0.046

Cross sections	Ω_1	Ω_2	Ω_3
D_1	1.2	1.2	1.2
D_2	0.4	0.4	0.2
$\Sigma_{r,1}$	0.03	0.03	0.051
$\Sigma_{a,2}$	0.3	0.25	0.04
$\Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}$	0.015	0.015	0.05
$\nu \Sigma_{f,1}$	0.0075	0.0075	0
$\nu \Sigma_{f,2}$	0.45	0.375	0

Figure 3. The simplified C5G7 Geometry Table II. Cross sections (cm^{-1}) for the simplified C5G7 benchmark

Figure 4. Neutron flux and the deviation from the reference solution for the simplified C5G7 benchmark with Sobol sampling method and Sin activation function.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the MF-PINNs are shown to provide highly accurate approximate solutions for the multi-group neutron diffusion equation. However, several challenges remain, such as the rapid growth of computational cost with the number of energy groups, the loss imbalance across energy groups in the training process, and potential convergence issues for k-eigenvalue problems. Future work will focus on addressing these challenges and extending this approach to three-dimensional problems such as the TWIGL 3D and Takeda benchmarks. In addition, applying MF-PINNs to the simplified PN (SPN) equations is another promising research direction.

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